

Innovative and Sustainable Groundwater Management in the Mediterranean

M2.3 First draft of Groundwater Trend Analysis Performed

VERSION 1

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Executive Summary

The overall objective of the InTheMED project is to implement innovative and sustainable management tools and remediation strategies for MED aquifers (inland and coastal) in order to mitigate anthropogenic and climate-change threats by creating new long-lasting spaces of social learning among different interdependent stakeholders, NGOs, and scientific researchers in five field case studies. These are located at the two shores of the MED basin, namely in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Tunisia, and Turkey.

InTheMED will develop an inclusive process that will establish an ensemble of innovative assessment and management tools and methodologies including a high-resolution monitoring approach, smart modelling, a socio-economic assessment, web-based decision support systems (DSS) and new configurations for governance to validate efficient and sustainable integrated groundwater management in the MED considering both the quantitative and qualitative aspects.

This is the Milestone 2.3, which summarises the work of Task 2.3: "Regional Groundwater Trends and Trajectories Analysis and Their Controlling Factors". This report analyzes the quantitative status of groundwater bodies in the Mediterranean region to identify variations and significant changes. The study utilizes historical groundwater level data to identify trends and significant changes, with a focus on detecting trends in groundwater levels. The study uses a statistical method called Mann-Kendall to identify trends and applies three different versions of the MK test. The study found that 40% of wells showed significant trends, with 63% of those showing declining and 37% showing rising levels. Most piezometers did not have a significant trend, ranging from 60% of the piezometers in the different countries.

1. Introduction

The Mediterranean region is facing significant water security challenges due to the increasing water demand and the effects of climate change. In this context, groundwater has become a crucial resource for irrigation and water supply in the region since the mid-20th century. Groundwater is a strategic resource for domestic supply, agriculture, and other economic activities but is also an essential part of ecosystems. Intense groundwater abstractions exceeding recharge can lead to long-term depletion with catastrophic consequences on streamflow and groundwater-dependent ecosystems, as well as land subsidence and salt-water intrusion in aquifers. However, the budget of this resource remains poorly understood, which makes it challenging to manage sustainably. Analyzing historical groundwater level data is one way to identify variations in the quantitative status of groundwater bodies across the region and to understand their complex dynamics. Groundwater level changes are influenced by several factors such as climate variability, recharge patterns, soil permeability, hydrogeology, land use, and groundwater abstraction.

One of the objectives of InTheMED is to strengthen the understanding of groundwater functioning and trends. Work Package 2 is focused on acquiring historical MED data, analyzing and sharing of collected data, and enriching data availability, using the High-Resolution Monitoring Approach (HRMA) in case studies characterized by limited data conditions. This report aims to characterize the changes in groundwater storage with a regional perspective, using the available groundwater quantity data from monitoring networks. As this work package was done with a regional perspective, the analysis of France is also included despite not being one of the partner countries of this project. First, an overview of the available time series data is conducted. Then, a description of the methods and results is analysed.

2. Data and Methods

In Deliverable 2.2, the collection of groundwater level time series is described in detail. A large portion of them is not centralized and openly accessible, resulting in a lack of detailed assessment of groundwater status at the regional Mediterranean scale. The groundwater monitoring networks of the partner InTheMED countries were analysed to understand the existing data. Furthermore, data that was openly accessible was collected, developing a database with over 9,500 piezometers.

2.1. Collected Time Series

All MED partner countries have groundwater level monitoring systems. National scale authorities enforce monitoring requirements, while subnational authorities, either province or river basin operators, handle monitoring and data production for the local groundwater bodies. In some cases, like Greece, Portugal, Spain, and Turkey, the data is collated and centralized by the national authority to build a national database. In other cases, the data are sparse in the different subnational authorities with different formats, captured variables, and quality standards, like in Italy and Tunisia.

We have built a database by obtaining data from several sources, processing it for quality checks and metadata creation, and then structuring the data into a standard format. We tailored a strategy for each country with the rationale of obtaining the most extended possible time series from official sources. These strategies have included so far:

- Downloading data from centralized national monitoring systems. This was the case for Portugal and Spain.
- Requesting the data from sub-national authorities without a centralized national system. This was the case for Italy.
- Requesting local researchers to help obtain data where language barriers or data sharing policies made it difficult to consult directly with the relevant authorities. This was the case for Greece and Tunisia.
- We have also collected data from public reports and published research. In Turkey groundwater level data sharing is very restricted.

Table 1. Existing groundwater data in different MED countries and their availabilities.

Country	Institutional data storage	Approximate amount of stations in the network	Approximate frequency of measurement	Publicly available online and gathered data	General length
Greece	Centralized	1,392	Seasonal, some annual	Yes	From 2010 to 2021 with gaps
Italy	Regional	3,970	Varies within regions from every three days to monthly	No	Increase of measurements in 1980 and 2000
Portugal	Centralized	990	Monthly (some daily)	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1980
Spain	Centralized	2,890	Monthly	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1985
France	Centralized	5,519	Weekly	Yes	Increase of measurements since 1960
Tunisia	Regional	3,100	Twice a year	No	Highly variable
Turkey	Regional	2,748	Varies from weekly to monthly	No	From 1970 on

We have obtained groundwater level data from 9,500 piezometers across the region, including all the countries in study cases of the InTheMED project and France. The time series lengths, frequency and completeness are contrasting. More data has been collected from countries with a central monitoring network that provide for a data sharing platform (Portugal, France and Spain). From the collected and processed data, groundwater level measurements started concentrating after 1980. Cumulatively, only 13% of the time series have 30 years or more of measurements, making it challenging to do long-term analysis. In Turkey, we collected data from only 27 stations; the figure doesn't reflect the growth of the network. In Greece the data collected is for 7 years only. In the case of Tunisia, the data processing of time series the processing of the data hasn't been completed as the sources. For these reasons, trends have only been calculated for Spain, Portugal, Italy and France.

2.2. Methodology

In this phase of our work, we focused on detecting trends in groundwater levels. Over time, changes can occur slowly or abruptly, and there are various statistical methods that can determine if such changes are significant. The choice of method depends on several factors, such as the length of the time series to ensure a sufficiently large sample, the correlation of one data point to the last one (autocorrelation), and the frequency of the measurements. The Mann-Kendall (MK) test is a widely used method for detecting trends in hydrological and groundwater levels. This test is based on ranking and does not require the assumption of normal distribution, which is often required by other methods. Studies by Fang et al. (2019), Lasagna et al. (2020), Lopez et al. (2015), Mirabbasi et al. (2020) and Ribeiro et al. (2015) have also used the Mann-Kendall test for similar purposes. Therefore, to detect trends in groundwater levels, we used the MK statistical method. We applied three different versions of the MK test to the annual average of water table depths, using a programming tool called pyMannKendall. The original MK test doesn't account for a phenomenon called autocorrelation, which can result in noise or false detections in the presence of trends. To address this, we tested a modification that removes autocorrelation before applying the test, as well as another modification that adjusts the variance based on the autocorrelation. The three tests identified trends in 40%, 14%, and 35% of the wells, respectively. To better understand the data, we also tested for autocorrelation using a test called Durbin Watson,

which showed a strong positive autocorrelation for most wells. Previous analysis revealed that the autocorrelation can lead to underestimating the presence of trends when using the pre-whitening modification (Yue and Wang, 2004). Therefore, we used the Hamed-Rao modification as the primary method for detecting trends.

At a first moment, groundwater level trends were assessed for the entire period of all piezometers with at least 10 years of data from Spain, Portugal, Italy, Turkey and France. A total of 7,179 piezometers were assessed at first. Then, at the moment of this report, only for Spain, Portugal and France, for the period between 1985 and 2014, trends were calculated for each decade to understand the dynamic of significant changes beyond one single trend direction and magnitude per time series.

3. Results

3.1. Entire Time Series

Out of the piezometers with a significant trend (40% with Hamed-Rao test), 63% had an increase of WTD (increasing depth related to depletion) and 37% a decrease. In the three analyzed countries, the majority of the piezometers didn't have a significant trend, ranging from 60-66% of the piezometers (Table 2). France had the highest percentage of increasing trend results, closely followed by Spain. Spain had the highest percentage of piezometers with a decreasing WTD. In the three countries, piezometers with increasing trend exceed those with a decreasing trend. While there is a similar distribution, it's important to notice that these tests reveal the trend along the entire time series, and any comparison should be careful, as the piezometers in the three countries have different starting times of measurement. As an example, some piezometers with overall increasing depth were observed in the near proximity to piezometers with overall decreasing depth. When looking closer, the overall increasing depth belonged to piezometers with several decades of data that had undergone depletion, and steady increase of depth, but later had a 'recovery phase' in the last decade. While the ones with overall decreasing depth had only been installed the last decades and only picked up on the 'recovery phase' of decreasing depth.

Table 2. MK trend test results for the entire period of each well with more than 10 years of data.

Country	Number of wells	Percentage of wells		
		No significant trend	Increasing depth	Decreasing depth
France	3,548	66%	24%	11%
Spain	1,557	60%	22%	18%
Italy	1,517	69%	13%	18%
Portugal	533	66%	16%	17%
Turkey	24	25%	71%	4%

Sen Slope is used to determine the magnitude of the apparent trends. This method calculates the median of all slopes between data pairs. The slope reflects the change of WTD, measured in meters, in an annual scale, so it can be understood as the change of meters per year in a piezometer. For piezometers with a significant trend to increase depth, most of the rates of

change (57%) are increasing in the range 0-0.2 meters per year, and up to 17% have a change rate from 0.2-0.4 meters per year; and up to 7% of the piezometers have a change rate greater than 1 meter per year. In the case of the piezometers with decreasing depth, also the majority (59%) is concentrated between 0-0.2 meters of decreasing depth per year, while up to 11% have a decrease of depth of more than 1 meter per year. The largest change rate of groundwater level has concentrated in the south west area of France, and the south east area of Spain (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Sen slope distribution of overall groundwater level change.

3.2. Decades Analysis

After analyzing the entire time series on each piezometer, an analysis was made for three decades in order to compare the changes from one period to another. This way, piezometers were chosen that had enough data for trend analysis from 1985 until 2014 in three segments (1985-1994, 1995-2004, 2005-2014), resulting in the analysis of only 843 piezometers. This way, it was possible to compare the amount of piezometers with a certain trend in the different periods to understand general trajectories of stability, increasing and decreasing WTD. The amount of piezometers with no significant trend fluctuated across the time periods (Figure 2), having the most (80%) in the second period. This is relevant as in the first period the amount of piezometers with an increasing WTD trend (associated to depletion) was up to 23%, and

then decreased to 13% in the second and third period. While the amount of piezometers with a decreasing WTD increased from 7% in the first and second period to 19% in the third period. These trajectories indicate a potential process of recovery from some depleting groundwater bodies.

Figure 2. Decade trend change from 1985-2014.

When looking at the spatial distribution of the decade analysis (Figure 3), a recovery process can be seen in the north of France, going from increasing depth piezometers populating the center of the country and the south west in 1985-1994, to then no trend and decreasing trends in 1995-2004 and then a bigger abundance of decreasing trend in the last decade. In a more dispersed manner, a similar process can be seen in Spain. However, in Portugal the opposite can be seen, while the first two decades show a mix of results, the last decade shows a more prevalent concentration of increasing WTD across the country.

Figure 3. Spatial distribution of decade analysis.

As mentioned previously, the first stage of the work has focused on the how the groundwater levels in the region have changed across time. Moving forward, the focus will be on analyzing the relationship with the factors driving change. For this end, we will continue with characterizing the relationships between groundwater level changes with precipitation and evapotranspiration products with gridded historical data. Then make a time dependent analysis of groundwater levels and land use change, by means of historical data. As well as trying to analyze the impact of groundwater use by identifying fitting proxies.

4. Closing Remarks

- The results of the study indicate that the majority of piezometers showing no significant trend, but there are significant trends in the depth of water tables across the studied regions, with Spain having the highest percentage of piezometers with a declining trend.
- The study found that piezometers with an declining trend in water table depth exceed those with a rising trend. However, it is important to note that the trend tests reveal the trend along the entire time series, and any comparison should be careful, as the piezometers in the three countries have different starting times of measurement.
- The decade analysis shows a potential process of recovery from some depleting groundwater bodies in the regions, with a decrease in the amount of piezometers with a declining trend and an increase in the amount of piezometers with a rising trend. The spatial distribution of the decade analysis shows a recovery process in the north of France and a more dispersed process in Spain, while Portugal shows a more prevalent concentration of increasing water table depth across the country. Moving forward, the focus will be on analyzing the relationship with the factors driving change, such as precipitation, evapotranspiration, land use change, and groundwater use.

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